

Omdurman Islamic University

Faculty of Arts Department of English Language and Literature

A research graduating to obtain Bachelor degree under the heading:

**Investigating the difficulties of developing reading
skills that face beginners of English Language**

Researcher : Zainab Alhadi Ahmed

Supervisor : Pr. Alfadil Altaib

September 2024

Qur'anic verse

God does not impose on any soul a responsibility beyond its ability. Every soul receives whatever it gains and is liable for whatever it does. Lord, do not hold us responsible for our forgetfulness and mistakes. Lord, do not lay upon us the burden that You laid on those who lived before us. Lord, do not lay on us what we cannot afford. Ignore and forgive our sins. Have mercy on us. You are our Lord. Help us against the unbelievers.

﴿ لَا يُكَلِّفُ اللَّهُ نَفْسًا إِلَّا وُسْعَهَا لَهَا مَا كَسَبَتْ وَعَلَيْهَا مَا اكْتَسَبَتْ رَبَّنَا لَا تُؤَاخِذْنَا إِنْ نَسِينَا أَوْ
أَخْطَأْنَا رَبَّنَا وَلَا تَحْمِلْ عَلَيْنَا إَصْرًا كَمَا حَمَلْتَهُ عَلَى الَّذِينَ مِنْ قَبْلِنَا رَبَّنَا وَلَا تُحَمِّلْنَا مَا لَا طَاقَةَ
لَنَا بِهِ وَاعْفُ عَنَّا وَارْحَمْنَا أَنْتَ مَوْلَانَا فَانصُرْنَا عَلَى الْقَوْمِ الْكَافِرِينَ ﴾ .

[البقرة: 286]

Dedication

All thanks and praise to Allah, Lord of the Worlds, always and forever. To the man who I love my superhero my father, to the kind hearted and supporter of my life my mother . To my tower of strength my sisters and brothers not forgetting my nieces and nephews. To the people were there for me all the time my friends I love you all . At the end I want to thank me for believing , achieving, and doing all hard works .

Acknowledgement

All gratitude and appreciation for OIU community especially English language department, all my gratitude is for the teacher's staff and all thankful to my supervisor T.Alfadil no words describe my appreciation for the hard work and constituency you gave to make this research more than a dream that comes true.

Abstract

The main purpose of this study is to Investigate the difficulties of developing reading skills that face beginners of English Language.

This study attempt to adopt problems and challenges in reading skills of English Language learners in generally and to the beginners students in various educational settings.

And to test the learners' difficulties, the study use the data collection for a number of fifteen samples. Then the collected data were analyzed by the percentage method .

The research highlights some results which are the learners struggle more with vocabulary . Future instruction should emphasize vocabulary-building exercises.

Strategies such as phonics instruction, vocabulary building, guided reading, and providing regular practice with varied reading materials can help beginners gradually improve their reading skills.

المخلص

الغرض الرئيسي من هذه الدراسة هو التحقيق في صعوبات تطوير مهارات القراءة التي يواجهها مبتدئو اللغة الإنجليزية.

تحاول هذه الدراسة تبني المشكلات والتحديات في مهارات القراءة لدى متعلمي اللغة الإنجليزية بشكل عام وللطلاب المبتدئين في مختلف البيئات التعليمية.

ولاختبار صعوبات المتعلمين، استخدمت الدراسة جمع البيانات لعدد من خمسة عشر عينة. ثم تم تحليل البيانات المجمعة بطريقة النسبة المئوية.

يسلط البحث الضوء على بعض النتائج وهي

أن المتعلمين يجدون صعوبة أكبر في المفردات. يجب أن تؤكد التعليمات المستقبلية على تمارين بناء المفردات.

يمكن أن تساعد الاستراتيجيات مثل تعليم الصوتيات وبناء المفردات والقراءة الموجهة وتوفير التدريب المنتظم مع مواد القراءة المتنوعة المبتدئين على تحسين مهارات القراءة لديهم تدريجياً.

Table of Contents

1.	Chapter One	10
1.1	Introduction	10
1.2	Research Problem.....	10
1.3	The significance of the problem.....	10
1.4	Research Objectives	10
1.5	Research Questions	11
1.6	The research hypotheses.....	11
1.7	Delimitation.....	11
1.8	Organization	11
2.	Chapter Two : Literature review	14
2.1	Introduction	14
2.2	Causes of difficulties and factors	14
2.3	Previous Studies	15
3.	Chapter Three : Methodology.....	18
3.1	Introduction	18
3.2	population of Study	18
3.3	The sample of the study.....	18
3.4	data collection instrument	18
3.5	statistical measurement.....	18
3.6	validity of the test.....	19
4.	Chapter Four	21
4.1	Introduction	21
4.2	Learners' test.....	21

4.3	The analysis of the test	21
4.4	Testing the hypothesis	25
5.	Chapter Five.....	27
5.1	Introduction	27
5.2	Conclusion.....	27
5.3	The findings of the study:.....	27
5.4	Recommendation.....	28
5.5	References	29

Chapter One

1. Chapter One

1.1 Introduction

Reading is a fundamental skill in language learning, serving as a gateway to acquiring vocabulary, grammar, and comprehension abilities. For beginners of English, developing reading skills can be particularly challenging due to various linguistic, cognitive, and contextual factors. This research aims to investigate the specific difficulties that beginners encounter when learning to read in English and to propose strategies for overcoming these challenges.

1.2 Research Problem

Beginners often face significant obstacles when learning to read in English. These difficulties may include unfamiliarity with the alphabet, lack of phonemic awareness, limited vocabulary, difficulties with grammar, and issues with text comprehension.

1.3 The significance of the problem

The goal of this research recognizes the difficulties that beginner students face in developing reading skills. Understanding these challenges is essential for educators to design effective instructional strategies that address the unique needs of beginner readers.

1.4 Research Objectives

The general objectives of this research are to investigate the challenges faced by beginners in developing English reading skills.

Specifically to analyze how these challenges affect overall reading comprehension and fluency. Also to recommend strategies to improve the reading skills of English language beginners.

1.5 Research Questions

What are the primary difficulties that beginners encounter when learning to read in English ?

What role do teaching methods and materials play in overcoming these reading challenges ?

What are the most effective strategies for supporting beginners in developing strong reading skills ?

1.6 The research hypotheses

Beginners students faced primary difficulties when learn to read in English.

Teaching methods and materials play role in overcome reading challenges.

The strategies for supporting beginners in developing reading skills.

1.7 Delimitation

This study will be for beginners learners of English Language , including students in primary editions, adult learners, and ESL (English as a second language) learners in various educational settings.

1.8 Organization

This study consists of five chapters. Chapter one contains an introduction of the study, chapter two deals with literature review of the study, chapter three will

discuss the methodology of the study. Chapter four deals with results and discussions. At last chapter five will be about conclusion and the recommendations.

Chapter Two

Literature review

2. Chapter Two : Literature review

2.1 Introduction

Reading skill refers to the ability to interpret, comprehend, and engage with written text .It is a foundational skill in language acquisition, especially in learning English as a second or foreign language (ESL/EFL). According to A'isyah (2010)" Reading is one of the skills in learning English.It is defined as an understanding a message conveyed by writer through visual and non_ visual information ". And this means the actual words, sentences, context and background.

And as a beginner language learner , reading skill can be challenging , but with the right strategies , build vocabulary and starting with simple texts it can become manageable and learners can improve.

2.2 Causes of difficulties and factors

Developing reading skills can be challenging for beginners due to a variety of factors including linguistic differences, limited vocabulary, difficulty with phonics and lack of phonemic awareness.

The results of A'isyah (2010) that has published on problems in learning of reading showed that; for vocabulary, language teachers should give vocabulary, which is difficult for students first and then explain meaning of each difficult word in the mentioned list of vocabulary . So that introduce new words in context and using them in sentences and in familiar concepts that will help learners to build vocabulary and develop.

Likewise, he has mentioned that teachers should motivate their students to practice and pronounce difficult words for pronunciation .

That will help beginners understand the relationship between letters and sounds. Phonics instruction helps them decode words.

This literature review synthesizes research findings on the difficulties and factors faced by beginners in English when developing reading skills.

- **Cognitive and Linguistic Challenges**

One of the primary difficulties in learning to read in English for beginners is the complexity of the language itself, meaning that there is often not a straightforward correspondence between letters and sounds (phonemes). According to research by Share (2008), this can lead to confusion for learners .

- **Cultural and Contextual Influences**

Cultural background and context can either facilitate or hinder the development of reading skills. For instance, learners from literate cultures where reading is emphasized may find it easier to adapt to reading in English. Conversely, learners from oral cultures or those with limited exposure to print media may struggle with the concept of reading as a skill.

Furthermore, the cultural content of reading materials can either engage or alienate learners. Texts that are culturally relevant and familiar tend to be more engaging, while those that are distant from the learners' own experiences can be difficult to relate to and comprehend (Koda, 2005).

2.3 Previous Studies

Reading Difficulties and Second Language Learners

Snow, C. E., & Matthews, T. J. (2016).

This study provides a foundational understanding of the unique challenges faced by ESL learners, particularly those with limited exposure to English.

- Beginner Students' Perceptions Concerning Reading Comprehension.

Daniela Arellano Pérez Universidad Veracruzana, (2013) It is widely known that reading is one of the four main skills to develop when learning a second language.

- Reading development and difficulties

Kate Cain

John Wiley & Sons, (2010)

This accessible text brings together research on word reading and comprehension development, which are often treated separately, and provides a comprehensive and detailed introductory text to reading development and difficulties.

Chapter Three

Methodology

3. Chapter Three : Methodology

3.1 Introduction

Methodology in chapter three provides the methods of data collection, whether the difficulties faced by students in developing reading skills have positive impact or negative impact on beginners students , a test will be provided for the samples. percentage method will be used for data analysis.

3.2 population of Study

The study is provided to beginners learners in various educational settings.

3.3 The sample of the study

The sample will be taken from beginners learners of English Language , which are including students in primary editions , adult learners, and ESL (English as a second language) the test will be applied for students in various educational setting which are 15 members .

3.4 data collection instrument

The study will use a test as tool for collecting data. The test composed of a reading text with multiple questions include comprehension, vocabulary meaning and choosing questions.

3.5 statistical measurement

The researcher will use percentage method for the analysis of the test . The test were examined by the the supervisor.

3.6 validity of the test

The test were examined by the the supervisor.

Chapter Four

4. Chapter Four

4.1 Introduction

Chapter four deals with the analysis of the test that have been given to beginners learners.

4.2 Learners' test

The test composed of a reading text with comprehension, vocabulary and choosing questions. To collect the data, fifteen beginners learners answered ten questions and the errors were analyzed .

4.3 The analysis of the test

Sample number one:

Number of errors	3
Number of correct answers	6
Errors percentage	3%

Sample number two :

Number of errors	9
Number of correct answers	1
Errors percentage	9%

Sample number three :

Number of errors	4
Number of correct answers	6
Errors percentage	4%

Sample number four :

Number of errors	9
Number of correct answers	1
Errors percentage	9%

Sample number five :

Number of errors	4
Number of correct answers	6
Errors percentage	4%

Sample number six :

Number of errors	5
Number of correct answers	5
Errors percentage	5%

Sample number seven :

Number of errors	4
Number of correct answers	6
Errors percentage	4%

Sample number eight :

Number of errors	5
Number of correct answers	5
Errors percentage	5%

Sample number nine :

Number of errors	3
Number of correct answers	7
Errors percentage	3%

Sample number ten :

Number of errors	6
Number of correct answers	4
Errors percentage	6%

Sample number Eleven:

Number of errors	3
Number of correct answers	7
Errors percentage	3%

Sample number twelve:

Number of errors	5
Number of correct answers	5
Errors percentage	5%

Sample number thirteen:

Number of errors	6
Number of correct answers	4
Errors percentage	6%

Sample number fourteen:

Number of errors	7
Number of correct answers	3
Errors percentage	7%

Sample number fifteen:

Number of errors	8
Number of correct answers	2
Errors percentage	8%

In our study, we analyzed the performance of fifteen samples on a reading comprehension exercise about the solar system.

The overall group performance was 46%, with errors in comprehension questions and in vocabulary questions (34.29%).

The total number of mistakes is 81% Only three students scored 3% and three students scored 5% , while two students scored 9% which is the highest percentage of errors .

4.4 Testing the hypothesis

Hypothesis number one : Beginners students faced primary difficulties when learn to read in English.The test suggests that while the samples generally comprehend basic concepts, they struggle more with specific facts which is , vocabulary-building, the method of formulation and the structures of sentences. so this hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis number two: Teaching methods and materials play role in overcome reading challenges. According to the text that given to the samples using visual aids, simplified texts, and interactive techniques help overcome reading challenges by engaging learners and addressing their specific needs.

Chapter Five

5. Chapter Five

5.1 Introduction

This chapter deals with the conclusion, main results, and findings of the study.

5.2 Conclusion

This study investigates the difficulties of developing reading skills that face beginners of English Language. A test was conducted by the researcher . according to the data obtained and analyzed the results are:

5.3 The findings of the study:

- Learners may have difficulties with syntactic structures, especially in complex sentences.

- Beginner learners might apply reading patterns from their native language, causing confusion.

- The majority of the samples struggle with unfamiliar vocabulary, hindering comprehension.

- Limited access to reading materials in English may slow the development of reading skills.

- Most of the samples have lack of reading strategies.

- Vocabulary knowledge and reading practice play vital role in developing.

5.4 Recommendation

- Recommend to apply the learnt vocabulary to other similar situations.
- English original texts could be preferred by the teachers and encourage learners to read English materials .
- Recommend Strategies such as phonics instruction, vocabulary building, guided reading, and providing regular practice .

5.5 References

- Cain, K. (2010). Reading Development And Difficulties. John Wiley & Sons.
- Dr. Akbar Ali' , Nasim Gul , An Investigating Into The Reading Comprehension Problems Faced By Pakistani Students At University Level.
- Koda, K. (2005). Insights Into Second language Reading: A cross-linguistic approach. Cambridge University Press.
- Krashen, S. D. (1982). Principles And Practice In Second language Acquisition. Pergamon Press.
- Perfetti, C. A., & Stafura, J. (2014). Word knowledge in a theory of reading comprehension. Scientific Studies of Reading.
- Pérez, D. A. (2013). On the anglocentricities of current reading research and practice. Universidad Veracruzana.
- Share, D. L. (2008). On the anglocentricities of current reading research and practice.